

Dark SRF Fermilab Ultra-Sensitive Dark Photon Search - Experiment Modification Proposal

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Dear Dark SRF Experiment at Fermilab,

About your dark photons research and recent publication,

<https://arxiv.org/abs/2510.02427> *

IMHO and from my research experience [1] [2],

The problem is that you operate at the **far-field** of emission 1.3 GHz \rightarrow 23.06 cm wavelength. Separation of cavities (center-to-center) is at 60cm (more than 2λ separation center to center).

Please re-configure your experiment to operate in the **near-field** (less than 1λ separation center to center) and you potentially will see the empty receiver cavity to light up (i.e. normal photons, dark photons oscillation).

I would aim for a separation center to center of the two cavities no more than approx. $\lambda/2$ thus no more than 12 cm separation to ensure operation in the near-field of emission, Even if this would require the two cavities to be positioned in parallel or in overlapping in-series configuration:

Fig. 1 Proposed experiment modification for the experiment to probe the near-field.

I am aware that the main argument against the proposed near-field operation of the experiment is, that reducing the separation of the two cavities (emitter and receiver cavity) below 2λ wavelengths separation will

introduce quantum tunneling effect (evanescent EM wave) in the measurement making it impossible to distinguish if what you are measuring is dark photons or normal photons quantum tunneling?

But I ask, is it possible that quantum tunneling of normal photons observed in the near-field and dark photons are actually the same phenomenon? And those dark photons are responsible for the photonic QT? If this is the case, then we will be in front of a breakthrough discovery in physics and the dark sector.

Best Regards,

Dr. Emmanouil Markoulakis

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p.s. * Paper Data mining AI Assist: https://grok.com/share/bGVnYWN5LWNvcHk_2adf5c0e-e186-479a-bb8b-ab512bba3a03

References

[1] Emmanouil Markoulakis, Antonios Valamontes. Dark Photons and Their Correlation with The Dark Sector Gravitons and The Higgs Boson $H \rightarrow \gamma\gamma$ Decay. *International Journal of Physical Research* , 2025, 13 (2), pp.1 - 13. ([10.14419/xhvxrg97](https://doi.org/10.14419/xhvxrg97)). ([hal-05204263v2](https://arxiv.org/abs/2504.05204v2))

[2] Markoulakis, Emmanouil and Walker, William D. and Antonidakis, Emmanuel, Nonlocal or Possibly Superluminal Maxwell Displacement Current Observed in the Near-field of a Spherical Capacitor (April 11, 2024). *International Journal on Communications Antenna and Propagation (IRECAP)*, volume 14, issue 4, 2024[[10.15866/irecap.v14i4.24903](https://doi.org/10.15866/irecap.v14i4.24903)], Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4790873> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.15866/irecap.v14i4.24903>